

THE ESSENCE AND FORMATION OF THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SERVICES MARKET IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Abstract: This article examines the nature and emergence of higher education services in higher education institutions, the role they play in society today, the factors influencing the competitiveness of higher education services, and the relationship between graduate students and employers.

Keywords: state, non-state, private, joint education, graduate student, employer, educational services, competition in the higher education services market, factors and mechanisms of competitiveness

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, higher education is becoming one of the areas where new approaches to managing activities aimed at increasing socio-economic efficiency and accelerated development are actively being formed. We can also observe that management processes in higher education institutions are increasingly adapting to the conditions of entrepreneurial activity. Of course, market laws are also beginning to apply to higher education. At the same time, the activities of universities are not limited to achieving commercial efficiency; it remains important for society to recognize the social significance of a particular higher education institution and the quality of training its graduates.

METHODS

The research method is aimed at analyzing the nature and formation of the competitiveness of the higher education services market. In our study, various

hypotheses of scientists are analyzed using methods such as analysis and synthesis, and the significance of the hypotheses is highlighted in a comparative manner, while the author's personal development is included.

RESULT

The study of theoretical and methodological approaches to the management of educational services promotion in foreign countries has been carried out for a much longer time than similar studies conducted by domestic scientists. Thus, V. Zarges and F. Heberlin [1] in the 1980s formed a comprehensive theory of educational marketing, believing that educational institutions, as participants in market processes, should use marketing tools to increase their competitiveness. However, F. Kotler and N. Lee [2] emphasize that social marketing should be used in the management of university promotion, otherwise universities will turn into economic corporations and lose their characteristics as social and research institutions.

There are several general points of view on the essence and nature of educational services, which are equally accepted by domestic and foreign scientists:

– education as a set of services, the subject of which is the process of transferring knowledge within a certain socio-economic system (A.O.Chentsov [3], V.A. Kachalov [4], A.M.Strijov [5] and others;

– the purpose of educational services is to increase the intellectual capital of a person and develop his skills as a result of the activities of an educational organization (V.P. Kolesov, T. McKinley [6]);

– education as a specific educational product or economic intangible benefit aimed at satisfying the educational and cognitive needs of a person (Arutyunova A.E. [7], Lipkina E.D. [8], Pankrukhin A.P. [9]).

Education as a separate, specific type of activity emerged a long time ago,

during which the process of transferring knowledge, information and forming certain competencies, skills and qualifications in the student takes place. However, in the market sense, goods and educational services appeared only in the 20th century. This was due to the proposal to include education as a separate field of activity in the scope of state activities and to implement educational services, especially in the field of higher education, by public education organizations.

DISCUSSION

The idea of increasing the competitiveness of the higher education services market in our country is based on the Presidential Decree No. 5847 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 “On approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, which aims to develop the social sphere and economic sectors by creating a healthy competitive environment in the sector based on the establishment of state and non-state higher education institutions in the regions. [10]

Based on the results of the above study, we came to the conclusion that the educational services market is a sphere of economic relations between, on the one hand, students seeking to satisfy their needs for education and professional competence through the active acquisition of knowledge, qualifications and skills, and, on the other hand, employers who need graduates with knowledge, qualifications and skills, organizations and individuals that provide educational services professionally and legally in accordance with state requirements for the content, quality and technologies of providing educational programs, representing a unique brand.

Based on the characteristics of these markets and the number of identified objects, analyzing the competitiveness of a higher educational institution is a very

complex task, since it requires the development of an integrated method of research and assessment. The main concept that expresses the essence of market relations is competition. As a result, for more than two centuries, the problems of competition have been reflected in the work of researchers who have created numerous theories in this field of knowledge.

With the help of the conducted research, we have formed the specific features of the concept of competition in the market of higher education services. Competition in the market of secondary higher education services is an opportunity to actively compete in order to offer consumers the highest quality services and the best products (graduates), taking into account the interests of service users (students and employers), while offering a distinctive brand in order to achieve competitive advantages in a competitive environment.

The peculiarity of the activities of a higher educational institution is that its competitiveness can be assessed from the point of view of several subjects: applicants (and their parents), state customers (the Ministry of Education and Science of Uzbekistan or another ministry), employers in the form of commercial organizations and enterprises, etc. We considered it appropriate to study these subjects in 2 groups, calling them graduate students and employer companies. However, these subjects also pay attention to several factors when determining competitiveness. To determine these factors, we conducted research among 4 types of higher educational institutions in our country (state, non-state, foreign and joint educational programs). According to its results, mechanisms for ensuring the competitiveness of the higher education services market were developed. In order to systematize the factors, we divided them into international, social and educational process mechanisms.

International mechanism - establishes relations and cooperation with different countries, exchanges experience, knowledge and goods on an international scale. The factors of this mechanism that affect competitiveness are international teachers,

international students and international articles.

Social mechanism - this mechanism provides services of a higher education institution that are not related to the educational process and international activities. Examples of this include consulting, legal, technical, cultural, environmental services, as well as the region of residence of students and the level of employment.

Educational process mechanism - in this mechanism, which covers educational, methodological and scientific processes, such factors as the type of study, the course of study and the quality of study were identified as a result of our research.

CONCLUSION

In general, higher education institutions should take into account the specifics of the modern era associated with their survival in a fairly fierce competitive struggle. The organization of educational and scientific activities requires more and more elements of entrepreneurship in the classical sense of the word, which includes the following main points: 1) the formation of a complex of educational services that fully meets market needs; 2) taking an active position in the market of educational services and scientific research, creating appropriate mechanisms for promoting educational and scientific products; 3) developing the optimal price-quality ratio of educational services and intellectual products, etc.

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